

DAMAGE SELF-SENSING BEHAVIOR OF BASALT FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES MODIFIED BY ELECTROPHORETIC DEPOSITION

Dr. Dong XIANG

Associate professor

Southwest Petroleum University

Outline

1 **Background**

2 **Method**

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1 Background

Basalt fiber (BF) is a green and environmentally friendly high-performance fiber, with a much lower cost than aramid and carbon fibers.

The high chemical inertia and smooth surface of BF lead to its low bonding ability with the resin, and complex damage is difficult to detect. External detection equipment has many limitations.

2 Method

Orientated deposition of carboxylated CNTs on BF under an electrical field by EPD

The **interface bonding** is improved while making it **functional** with uniformly deposited CNTs .

3 Results

Structural characterization and interfacial performance of BFRP

CNTs in the modified interface causes cracks to deflect, preventing crack extension.

3 Results

Mechanical and electrical properties of BFRP modified by EPD

Sample	Resistivity ($\text{k}\Omega \cdot \text{mm}^{-1}$)	
	Cross-layer	Through-layer
BFRP	N/A	N/A
EPD5-BFRP	44.2(± 2.4)	895.3(± 9.4)
EPD10-BFRP	39.1(± 3.1)	600.4(± 7.0)
EPD15-BFRP	36.8(± 2.1)	313.78(± 3.8)
EPD20-BFRP	34.8(± 1.6)	233.4(± 7.1)
EPD25-BFRP	35.1(± 3.3)	247.6(± 1.3)

Optimal deposition voltage is 20 V

3 Results

Damage self-sensing of BFRP modified by EPD

Elastic strain

Tensile

Flexural

Tensile to break

Single-layer BFRP

Multi-layer BFRP

Functionalized single-layer and multi-layer BFRP exhibited similar electrical signal responses to tensile load. The acoustic emission (AE) signals agreed well with RRC.

3 Results

Single-layer

Multi-layer (lower EPD)

The multi-layer BFRP containing a single-layer EPD20-BFRP on the upper or lower surface of laminate exhibited distinct RCC under flexural loading.

Multi-layer (upper EPD)

4 Conclusions

- The tensile and flexural **moduli** of modified EPD-BFRP **increased by 37.5% and 14.9%** respectively.
- Single-layer EPD20-BFRP exhibited a **high gauge factor (GF) of 44.3** during tensile damage self-sensing.
- The **AE signals** during tensile and flexural damage process **agreed well with the RRC**, which confirmed different damage stages within loading process, such as elastic deformation, damage evolution, crack coalescence, and complete fracture.
- The multi-layer BFRP containing a single-layer EPD20-BFRP on the upper or lower surface of laminate exhibited **distinct electrical signal responses** under flexural loading, due to different strain states.

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Email: d.xiang@swpu.edu.cn